

CONTENT AND PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF PEDAGOGUES-EDUCATORS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Annotation: *The study of theoretical and methodological aspects of pedagogic and psychological peculiarities of preparation and improvement of pedagogic-pedagogical educational organization and improvement of methods and improvement of qualifications shows what is necessary for the creation of pedagogical conditions, training and quality organization of training and the development of professional skills.*

Key words and expressions: *Getting a quality education, advanced training, professional competence, effective methods and techniques, organizational and didactic system of the advanced training process, interactive methods, methodology of didactic research, system-complex diagnostics in pedagogical research.*

Аннотация: *Исследование теоретико-методических аспектов педагогических и психологических особенностей подготовки и повышения квалификации педагогов-воспитателей дошкольных образовательных организаций и совершенствование методов их повышения квалификации показывает, что существует необходимость создания педагогических условий, требующих качественной организации обучения в развитии профессиональных навыков и компетентности. Поэтому повышение квалификации педагогов-воспитателей дошкольных образовательных организаций рассматривается как социально-педагогическая проблема.*

Ключевые слова и выражения: *повышение квалификации, профессиональная компетентность, эффективные методы и приемы, организационно-дидактическая система процесса повышения квалификации,*

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev 2017 in the decision of September 9 PQ-3261 "On measures to fundamentally improve the preschool education system", the current system of personnel training and retraining focused on the problem of providing the field of preschool education with highly qualified specialists who are able to solve the issues of raising and all-round development of children at a professional level. passed. Therefore, improving the professional competence of pedagogues-educators of preschool educational organizations occupies a special place.

It is necessary to be aware of modern educational technologies in the development of pedagogical activities of teachers-educators.

The skills of applying interactive and modern methods to the educational process are formed in professional development courses. It is appropriate to develop the professional competence of the pedagogue-educator.

The pedagogues-educators working in are required to perform professional activities (management, social-pedagogical, correctional-developing), scientific outlook and cultural-spiritual moral qualities, special professional competence, that is, thorough knowledge of preschool education methodology.

In addition, pedagogues-educators should follow the criteria of professional competence. The criteria are as follows: ability to use modern technologies in practice; able to choose effective methods and tools; Knowledge of the content and areas of state requirements and implementation; Being able to apply the content of the "Ilk Kadam" state curriculum to different age groups; Monitoring of children's knowledge, skills and qualifications in the areas of state requirements; to have national and universal values, to participate in the social life of the country; respect for family and traditions; have social skills; sociability - knowing the language, communicating with different people, standing in a special place in the team; working on oneself, developing oneself physically, spiritually, intellectually.

Also, didactic competence requirements are imposed on the teacher.

First, create an interactive and media environment;

Secondly, predicting the coverage of the subject content in advance;

Thirdly, management of the educational process;

Fourthly, assessment of children's achievements and development;

Fifth, provide motivation and help to children;

Sixth is to understand and develop children's knowledge.

The listed didactic requirements are mastered by pedagogues-educators in the process of professional development. For this, it is appropriate to rely on androgogic principles in the educational process: independent education, cooperation, use of life experiences, individual approach, selectivity, reflexivity, continuity.

These principles are an important factor in improving the professional competence of pedagogues-educators.

Communicative competence also occupies a special place in improving the professional competence of educators. Because the subject-subject relationship is effective in quality organization of education. This requires pedagogues-educators to follow the rules of socio-linguistic - correct expression of speech, discursive - to express thoughts in a logical sequence, to support them in the process of talking with children.

A pedagogue-educator of preschool educational organizations should have national and spiritual values, intellectual, informational, motivational, cognitive, i.e. knowledge activity, reflexive self-analysis skills.

Organization of quality education in the rapidly changing socio-economic conditions, as well as modernization of the field of preschool education, primarily depends on the personal and professional views of the pedagogue-educator, i.e. competitiveness, new thinking, cognitive development, high level of personal qualities and capabilities. If he does not have the qualifications and skills specific to his profession, he cannot become a teacher at the level of demand. For this, the pedagogue-educator should have pedagogical skills and be able to organize the educational process in a qualitative manner.

Andijan, Samarkand, and Tashkent regional centers of the regional centers of educational institutions of preschool education organizations, based on our

experiences for several years (2018-2020) in training courses for teachers, and based on the results of observing the participation and behavior of teachers in educational activities, effective teaching of modern technologies in the training process. , it was also determined that they should develop the skills and abilities to use technologies. Studying the activity of pedagogues-educators of the preschool education organization during the trial period showed that there are certain shortcomings in this direction.

They can be described as follows:

that pedagogues-educators do not have enough organizational, pedagogical-methodical knowledge, skills and qualifications to effectively implement the preschool education process;

that high results are not being achieved in updating the training plans of the advanced training courses;

low motivation of pedagogues-educators in relation to the training course (under the influence of work activity, experience, needs, interests and desires, health);

not fully using the necessary tools and opportunities in developing the professional competence of pedagogues-educators;

the fact that pedagogues-educators are not ready for innovative activities during the professional development course, they cannot effectively use personal-oriented education and information technologies in pedagogical activities;

insufficient formation of communicative, diagnostic, reflexive, organizational, skills in educators;

that the criteria for professional monitoring and assessment of the psychological preparation of pedagogues-educators and their attitude to the innovation process have not been developed;

insufficient number of highly educated pedagogues-educators;

lack of improvement of the model of improving the professional competence of pedagogues-educators.

1. The shortcomings mentioned above are clearly visible in the process of improving the activity and qualification of pedagogues-educators of preschool educational organizations. In our opinion, the elimination of existing shortcomings requires the following:
2. 1. Further improvement of social, methodical and pedagogical requirements for raising the qualifications of pedagogues-educators of preschool educational organizations;
3. 2. Effective application of modern and information technologies in the process of improving the qualifications of pedagogues-educators;
4. 3. Creating an organizational and didactic system of continuous professional development of teachers;
5. Implementation of an integrative approach in improving the qualifications of pedagogues-educators of the preschool education organization;
6. Ensuring the priority of the principles of formation of social-cultural, pedagogical-psychological, regulatory-legal skills in the development of professional competence.
7. Organization of education aimed at the comprehensive formation of the educator's personality in the process of qualification improvement, achieving the enrichment of this process with humanitarian and democratic ideas.

Professional training, creativity is considered the mechanism of development of the pedagogue's personality, pedagogical skill is considered the quality of creativity. Pedagogical skill is the most necessary description of pedagogical activity. Pedagogical skill is the law of creative formation of personality.

During the training course, the pedagogical skills of pedagogues-educators are developed based on the use of interactive educational methods in training. "Interactive" means interaction, mutual action, joint activity.

Professional and personal qualities of educators are changed and improved in the interactive process. Helping educators to justify their thoughts and experience, to believe, to listen to others, to design their personal knowledge in the educational process is one of the most urgent problems of education today. In the process of

interactive education, there is a situation of finding a solution "at this place and at this time" instead of spending a certain period of time, and then the opinions expressed by the audience are analyzed.

Effective use of time in training is a necessary condition in the process of training. For this purpose, professors and teachers need to choose the necessary tools, forms and technologies correctly.

The use of modern technologies plays an important role in improving the professional competence of pedagogues. As a result, the active participation of the audience and their interests will come to the main stage, the goal will be achieved through their proper orientation, adherence to didactic requirements, and the priority of person-oriented education. Gaps in professional activity are filled through methods and technologies selected according to the needs of educators. By reflexive analysis of the learning process, it is possible to design future learning processes. This requires the use of project technology in the educational process. In the process of designing, attention is paid to effective assimilation of the standards of pedagogical activities of pedagogues-educators, to adapt them to their pedagogical activities, and to correct their professional views based on their personal experiences. Such an approach develops the professional competence of the pedagogue-educator, creates the ability to use a new approach in his professional activity.

In our country, practical activities are being carried out to modernize preschool education. Consequently, the scientific-methodical basis of the process of education and training of the young generation and qualified specialists was developed, and the continuous education system operating in a new content and direction at the level of the world standard was improved.

At the moment, it is a matter that cannot be delayed to improve the activities of educators working in the preschool education system, which is the first link of continuous education, to implement the most advanced and unique ideas in the content of the qualification process.

Updating the content and methods of training in the system of professional development guarantees the achievement of quality education. Changing and updating the content of in-service education helps to increase the professional competence of educators. In particular, in today's rapidly changing era, the need for educators to introduce scientific innovations and use best practices in the preschool education process is increasing.

Modern problems in the preschool education system require the educator to acquire a new professional and personal quality, systematic creative thinking, information, communicative culture, competitiveness, leadership qualities, life aspirations and high self-confidence, the ability to create a positive image of oneself, the ability to analyze one's own activities with awareness, It requires the ability to act independently in any situation, to maintain a healthy lifestyle, and to have stable emotions.

In order to create a new creative and healthy environment in preschool education, it is necessary to update the content of education, to determine the main aspects of raising the professional activity of teachers, to organize their professional and pedagogical qualifications in new ways during the training process.

The quality of pedagogic personnel is the most necessary component in the preschool education system. Because the implementation of all other components depends on how the educational system is organized.

The main task of educators of pre-school educational organizations is to teach them to think and think in accordance with the times on the basis of advanced pedagogical technologies in preparing the growing young generation for school education.

Each tutor algorithm monitors the plan in cooperation with the teacher of the training course. At the end of the course there will be a general analysis. Educators develop the dynamics of the acquired knowledge. This process ensures effective reflexive activity.

The result of the methodical service provides an opportunity to achieve success in the development of the professional skills of educators in preschool educational

organizations, in choosing the most optimal methods of preparing students for school education.

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